

NOTES

Chemical Constituents of the Roots of *Canscora decussata*. Part II

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In a previous paper we have reported¹ the occurrence of sixteen xanthenes, having 'standard' 1,3,5- and 1,3,7-trioxygenated systems and, in some cases, with added oxygen functions at C-6, C-7 and/or C-8 positions, in the roots of *Canscora decussata* Schult. (Gentianaceae)².

Further investigation has resulted in the isolation of a number of known and new triterpene, alkaloid and xanthone constituents. Preliminary chemical studies of these compounds constitute the subject of the present communication.

Petroleum (60–80°) extract (Soxhlet) of the ground roots (2.4 kg), after removal of weak bases and minor phenolic constituents, afforded several triterpene constituents, separated by solvent extraction and preparative chromatography. These are identified as β -amyrin (m.p., mixed m.p., co-t.l.c., $[\alpha]_D$, i.r.; m.p. and mixed m.p. of the acetate), friedelin (m.p., mixed m.p., co-t.l.c., $[\alpha]_D$, M⁺, m/e), and epifriedelanol (m.p., mixed m.p., co-t.l.c., $[\alpha]_D$, i.r., m/e). In addition, two apparently new triterpene acids were isolated from the sparingly soluble petroleum fraction. Structure elucidation of these compounds will be the subject of a later communication.

The defatted roots afforded mangiferin (45 g.) during hot alcohol extraction. The EtOH extract was concentrated, the thick slurry taken in aqueous AcOH (4%, 200 ml), the AcOH suspension was thoroughly shaken with CHCl₃ (ten 100 ml portions) to separate non-nitrogenous compounds in the organic layer. The clarified aqueous solution upon basification (NH₃) and usual processing of the liberated bases gave gentianine (m.p., base hydrochloride, m.p., base nitrate, m.p.) and a new amorphous glycoalkaloid. Liberal amounts of choline and another quaternary base of undetermined constitution were obtained from the water-soluble fraction through their reineckates³.

The combined CHCl₃-extracts (1 l) was concentrated to give a brown amorphous material (0.95 g). It was triturated with EtOH (25 ml) and the less soluble fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Early CHCl₃ eluates afforded yellow needles (86 mg). The compound showed a complex u.v. spectrum characteristic of hydroxyxanthenes and a broad melting range, 245–252°, and was clearly a mixture. Mass spectrometry indicated

1. R. K. Chaudhuri and S. Ghosal, *Phytochem.*, 1971, 10, (in press).
2. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, p. 49, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956.
3. S. Ghosal, P. K. Banerjee and S. K. Banerjee, *Phytochem.*, 1970, 9, 429.

presence of four xanthenes in the ratio shown in parenthesis : (i) a tetrahydroxydimethoxyxanthone, M^+ 320 (26); (ii) a trihydroxytrimethoxyxanthone, M^+ 334 (42); (iii) a penta-methoxyxanthone, M^+ 346 (12); (iv) a hexamethoxyxanthone, M^+ 376 (20). Repeated preparative t.l.c. of the xanthone mixture over neutral and acidic (H_2SO_4) chromatoplates (silica gel G, E. Merck), using PhH-EtOAc as developer, resulted in the separation of these xanthenes into three distinct zones. Xanthenes (iii and iv), being least polar, were obtained from the upper zone, while from the middle and lower zones xanthone (i) and xanthone (ii), respectively, were obtained.

Xanthone (iv), $C_{19}H_{20}O_8$, m.p. 158–161°, showed u.v. λ_{max} (EtOH) 205, 240–42^{*}(sh), 250, 280 (inflec.), 325, 335 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.1, 4.2, 4.33, 3.92, 3.98, 4.1); i.r. ν_{max} (KBr) 1670 cm^{-1} (xanthone C = O); n.m.r. spectrum ($CDCl_3$) showed six methoxylgroups at τ 5.9–6.05 (18 H), and two aromatic protons appeared as *meta* split doublets centered at τ 3.58 (C_4 -H) and 3.73 (C_2 -H). Mass spectrum of the xanthone showed molecular-ion peak at m/e 376 and significant peaks at m/e 361, 348, 347, 346, 333 (metastable peak appeared at 320.5; 376 \rightarrow 347 requires m^* , 320.2). On the basis of these data the xanthone is identified as 1,3,5,6,7,8-hexamethoxyxanthone.

The two other hexaoxygenated xanthenes (i) and (ii), obtained through the preparative t.l.c., gave the same 1,3,5,6,7,8-hexamethoxyxanthone on complete methylation. Assignment of the methyl groups in these xanthenes is currently under way.

This is for the first time that hexamethoxy- and other hexaoxygenated xanthenes are found in the family Gentianaceae. Only one hexaoxygenated xanthone, viz., 1,2,3,4,6,7-hexamethoxyxanthone, has previously been reported⁴ to occur in nature (*Polygala macradenia*).

The hexaoxygenated xanthenes from the genus *Canscora* share with none their oxidation pattern, based on a 'standard' 1,3,5-trihydroxy xanthone structure with additional oxygenation at C-6, C-7, and C-8 positions. This may have significant taxonomic value, at least in the generic level, and further work in this direction is in hand.

The authors are indebted to Dr. B. Das, CNRS, Gif-Sur-Yvette, France, for the mass spectra and to Dr. N. M. Khanna, CDRI, Lucknow, for the n.m.r. and i.r. spectra. Two of them (R.K.C. and A.N.) are grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding research fellowships.

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Received December 15, 1970

4. D. L. Dreyer and L. David, *Tetrahedron*, 1969, **25**, 4415.